

Olive/holm Oaks Traditional Systems in Andalucia Promoting Ecosystem Services

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Vegetation cover management in olive groves using sheep.

The centenary olive groves in *Andalucia* represent a unique agricultural and cultural heritage with immense potential. The extra virgin olive oil from these olive groves is valued for its organoleptic characteristics and the its agricultural ecosystem promoting sustainable agricultural practices favouring the olive grove ecosystem health and the rural communities well-being. Moreover, these olive groves preservation keep alive a cultural heritage and encourages rural and cultural tourism, attracting visitors interested in the history and production of olive oil. Centenary olive trees combined with boundary *holm* oaks linked to *Hojiblanca*, *Picudo* and *Picual* varieties placed in 24 ha farms with an average productivity of 4,500kg of olives/ha are representative of these ecosystems. *Holm* oaks-olive tree combinations sequester more carbon and maintain a high level of biodiversity associated with food production and enhancing auxiliary niche becoming relevant for beekeeping settlement. The *holm/oak-olive* ecosystem is usually related to intercropping with grazed grass and legumes, playing a crucial role to preserve soil health, reducing erosion and also promoting biodiversity that enhances ecosystem services improving soil moisture by reducing evapotranspiration, while protecting against the impact of heavy rainfall, resulting in increased water retention. Soil health is also improving by favouring the biological activity of the soil, increasing the presence of beneficial micro-organisms. Representative farms (24 ha) are grazed by 300 sheep from the beginning of March to the end of April reducing the competition for water between the cover and olive trees and the above-ground biomass and the fire risk of fire in the summer season. Sheep grazing also reduces the environmental impact by reducing carbon footprint linked to mechanical clearing and fertilization, while enhancing food security by reducing the use of herbicides. Traditional *holm/olive* grows grazing contributes to the sustainability of a highly demanded product, while promoting the economic development of rural areas.

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